
Appropriate Technology Movement: An Overview

Dr. Dhanaji Dattatray Patil

Assit. Prof. Dept. of Sociology,

D. R. Mane Mahavidhalaya, Kagal

Corresponding Author – Dr. Dhanaji Dattatray Patil

DOI - 10.5281/zenodo.15067274

Introduction:

First of all is necessary to understand the concept of Appropriate Technology. In this regard, as Kumar (2002) points out, “improved management of natural resources in the light of proper engineering, technological and business practices combined with both the order, indigenous knowledge and the modern agro industrial technologies, biotechnology, informatics and micro-electronics can go a long way in preventing further damage and restoring the earth system by introducing feedbacks on climate which can help stabilize and regulate its environment. In the past, ‘appropriate’ technology used to be considered under the ‘small is beautiful’ frame. It has now advanced to a level expressing what technology should really be about anyway – a means of enhancing the livelihood of humankind in tune with a healthy and clean environment” (Kumar H.D.: 2002).

Many people are coming to realize that neither our economy nor our population can continue to grow forever. We are running out of the natural resources necessary to sustain ourselves. In addition we are limited in our ability to deal with the social and environmental problems that result from continuous growth. There seems to be a growing dissatisfaction with the complexity and hectic lifestyle of 20th century society. Many people would prefer to return to a simpler way of life.

Appropriate technology is attractive because it makes households and industries more self-sufficient, and most things can be managed at a local level. We may have to do more hand labour instead of depending on automation to satisfy our basic needs. However, there are many advantages to simplifying our lives. By growing more of our own food and producing and buying goods in our own communities, we spend less time and money on transportation, produce less waste and consume fewer environmental resources(<http://lsa.colorado.edu/essence/texts/appropriate.htm>).

We should think of eco-friendly technology. Alternative technology is a term sometimes used by environmental advocates to refer to technologies which are more environmentally friendly than the functionally equivalent technologies dominant in current practice. There are many factors which may be cited as implying greater environmental friendliness, such as greater efficiency, or different fuels or power sources. The term also includes products or production processes that promote or enhance material recovery, recycling or marketing of secondary materials, or that reduce or eliminate waste or emissions at the source of generation (<http://www.daenvis.org/introessat.htm>).

The term “Environmentally Sound Appropriate Technology” (ESAT) is

amalgamation of two terms; environmentally sound technology and appropriate Technology. An environmentally sound technology is a technology that serves the goals of development and also reduces the risk of harm to human health (or the environment), enhancing cost-effectiveness (of achieving environmental protection), improving process efficiency, and creating products and processes that are environmentally beneficial. Appropriate Technology is a term that represents the social and cultural dimension of innovation. The idea here is that the value of a technology lies not only in its economic viability and its technical soundness, but also in its adaptation to the local social and cultural environment. Taken together, ESAT is a technology that has two considerations. Firstly, it protects the environment, is less polluting, uses all resources in a more sustainable manner and secondly, it springs from indigenous creativity in response to local needs and possibilities.

The Environmentally Sound Appropriate Technology, primarily, shares three characteristics:

1. It is relevant and ready for use by the common people and aims directly to improve the quality of their lives.
2. It derives maximum leverage from the local cultural environment, by drawing upon the existing managerial and technical skills and providing the basis for extending them.
3. It uses the physical potential of an area, and maintains man's harmony with nature.

Assessing the appropriateness of a technology necessarily involves some sort of value judgment, both on the part of the developer of technology as well as the user of technology. This also implies that a technology that is environmentally sound and appropriate in one condition may be inappropriate in a different condition, meaning thereby that (ESAT) is a condition

specific technology, a relative notion that varies in space and time (www.daervis.or.htm).

The concept of "Appropriate Technology" can be outlined as follows:

1. The design of technology is more in response to the local needs, thus it promotes ingenuity of the local people.
2. It compliments human labour and skills rather than attempting to replace human labour and eliminating human skills; there is an effort to make the human element more productive and creative.
3. The processes and procedures involved are simple, at which people without sophisticated management training can work together and understand what they are doing.
4. It allows a more economical operation by minimizing the transport of goods in an era of expensive energy, allowing greater interaction of local industry and permitting greater use of local resources (both human as well as material).
5. It makes unnecessary many expensive or unavailable finance, transportation, education advertising, and management and energy services; and avoids the loss of local control that the use of such outside services implies.
6. It helps to establish a self-sustaining and expanding reservoir of skills in the community, which begins from already existing skills;
7. It tends towards decentralization of production, thus permitting the full benefits of work to remain within a community; this also allows the control to remain within community;
8. It provides a region with a cushion against the effects of outside economic changes (e.g. the sudden unavailability of fertilizer);
9. It helps to reduce economic, social and political dependency between individuals, between regions, and between nations, by recognizing that

people can and will do things for themselves if the obstacles to this are removed.

10. It is in harmony with the cultural traditions of the area; this does not mean it is stagnant, but that it evolves along with the culture; and does not contradict values the people believe to be important. (www.daervis.or.htm).

In a nutshell, ‘Appropriate Technology’ is harmonious to use social and cultural level. It will decrease the adverse effect of traditional technology which most of use. Now, it is necessary to see the origin and history of the appropriate technology movement at length.

The Statement of the Research Problem:

The social, economic and environmental impact of appropriate technologies on the beneficiaries of such technologies has not received much research attention from social scientists. This is more so in India where 68.08% (2011, Census) of the population lives in the villages, where majority of population is illiterate and this has inhibited the use of appropriate technology for sustainable development. ‘Alternative and Appropriate Technology’ has emerged as a key instrument for influencing the process of development especially after 1990s. It is because of this that there is a paucity of studies in this area. Hence it has motivated the researcher to undertake the proposed study.

Objectives of the Study:

The specific objectives of the study were as under:

1. To study the emergence of the appropriate technology movement.

Research Methodology:

The following methodological procedures are adopted for present investigation.

Type of Research Design:

With regards to the nature of this kind of study, the descriptive research design has been adopted for the present study.

Tools and Techniques Used For Data Collection:

For the present study secondary sources of data are used. Secondary sources of data are mainly collected from various project proposals, project reports, government reports, books, journals, articles, encyclopedia, dictionaries, periodicals, government and non-government web sites.

Appropriate Technology Movement:

Appropriate technology is an ideological movement (and its manifestations) originally articulated as “intermediate technology” by the economist Dr. Ernst Friedrich “Fritz” Schumacher in his influential work, “Small is Beautiful”. Though the nuances of appropriate technology vary between fields and applications, it is generally recognized as encompassing technological choice and application that is small scale, labour intensive, and energy efficient, environmentally sound and locally controlled (Hazeltine, B.; Bull, C.:1999:3). Both Schumacher and many modern-day proponents of appropriate technology also emphasize the technology as people centered.

Appropriate technology is most commonly discussed in its relationship to economic development and as an alternative to transfers of capital-intensive technology from industrialized nations to developing countries (<http://www.amazon.com>).

However, appropriate technology movements can be found in both developing and developed countries. In developed countries, the appropriate technology movement grew out of the energy crisis of

the 1970s and focuses mainly on environmental and sustainability issues (<http://www.ncat.org>).

Appropriate technology has been used to address issues in a wide range of fields. The well-known examples of appropriate technology applications include: bike- and hand-powered water pumps (and other self-powered equipment), the universal nut Sheller, self-contained solar-powered light bulbs and streetlights, and passive solar building designs.

Generally appropriate technology is proving sustainable. It is small scale, labour intensive, energy efficient and most important thing is environmentally sound. In our country Mahatma Gandhi is the pioneer of this movement. His concept of Self-Reliance is the heart of appropriate technology. So we should study his concept of Self-Reliance in detail.

Mahatma Gandhi: Concept of Self-Reliance:

Indian ideological leader Mahatma Gandhi is often cited as the “father” of the appropriate technology movement. Though the concept had not been given a name, Gandhi advocated for small, local and predominantly village-based technology to help India’s villages become self reliant. He disagreed with the idea of technology that benefited a minority of people at the expense of the majority or that put people out of work to increase profit (<http://scholar.lib.vt.edu>).

In 1925 Gandhi founded the All-India Spinners Association (AISA) and in 1935 he retired from politics to form the All-India Village Industries Association (AIVIA) both organizations focused on village-based technology similar to the future appropriate technology movement (<http://www.mk Gandhi.org>).

Mahatma Gandhi advocated small, local, mostly village-based technology to help India’s villages become self reliant,

resisting the dependence associated with colonialism, to aid in the freedom struggle against British and wealthy Indians.

Gandhi promoted the philosophy of “swadeshi” or self-reliance. He did not believe that technological development was inherently synonymous with progress. He believed the powers of technology should be produced and used artfully and the benefits should be close to the individual and widely produced and distributed in a decentralised fashion. Gandhi stated that his favourite technologies were the sewing machine, because it was invented out of love, and the bicycle, because it kept one’s feet close to the ground. He felt that technology should not disenfranchise people or be used for violence - rather that it should be used to empower people broadly. The movement for self-rule was based on local economies, and Gandhi championed the spinning wheel, or charka, employed in the khadi movement in the 1920s, which produced cloth locally in an act of civil disobedience, causing the British monopoly on textiles to collapse. The spinning wheel is today seen at the centre of the Indian national flag, and the flag itself must, by law, be made of khadi.

In India, our father of nation M. K. Gandhi promoted the concept of ‘Self-Reliance’ or ‘Swadeshi’. He accepted the all rural development of man including spiritual which is very close to appropriate technology as a term appropriate technology was invented by E. F. Schumacher in his book, ‘Small is Beautiful’.

E. F. Schumacher: Small is Beautiful:

Dr. Ernst Friedrich “Fritz” Schumacher is credited as the founder of the appropriate technology movement. A well-known economist, Schumacher worked for the British National Coal Board (BNCD) for more than 20 years, where he blamed the size of the industry’s operations for its uncaring response to the harm black-lung disease inflicted on the miners

(<http://scholar.lib.vt.edu>). However it was his work with developing countries, such as India and Burma that helped Schumacher to form the underlying principles of appropriate technology. Schumacher first articulated the idea of “intermediate technology,” now known as appropriate technology, in a 1962 report to the Indian Planning Commission (IPC) in which he described India as long in labour and short in capital, calling for an “intermediate industrial technology” that harnessed India’s labour surplus. Schumacher had been developing the idea of intermediate technology for several years prior to the Planning Commission report. In 1955, following a stint as an economic advisor to the government of Burma, he published the short paper “Economics in a Buddhist Country,” his first known critique of the effects of western economics on developing countries (McRobie, George: 1981,:19). In addition to Buddhism, Schumacher also credited his ideas to Gandhi.

Initially, Schumacher’s ideas were rejected by both the Indian government and leading development economists. Spurred to action over concern the idea of intermediate technology would languish, Schumacher, George Mc-Robie, Mansur Hoda and Julia Porter brought together a group of approximately 20 people to form the Intermediate Technology Development Group (ITDG) in May of 1965. Later that year, a Schumacher article published in the Observer garnered significant attention and support for the group. In 1967, the group published the ‘Tools for Progress: A Guide to Small-scale Equipment for Rural Development’ and sold 7,000 copies. ITDG also formed panels of experts and practitioners around specific technological needs (such as building construction, energy and water) to develop intermediate technologies to address those needs (McRobie, George: 1981,:19). At a conference hosted by the ITDG in 1968 the

term “intermediate technology” was discarded in favour of the term “appropriate technology” used today. Intermediate technology had been criticized as suggesting the technology was inferior to advanced technology and not including the social and political factors included in the concept put forth by the proponents (<http://scholar.lib.vt.edu>). In 1973, Schumacher described the concept of appropriate technology to a mass audience in his influential work, “Small is Beautiful: Economics as if People Mattered”.

In this context, we should understand the concept of Victor Papanek’s ‘Design for Human Scale’.

Papanek: Design for Human Scale:

Victor Papanek wrote about similar concepts in the context of design of everyday products. His writing is full of examples of appropriate and inappropriate designs (without necessarily using those terms) and is an inspiring introduction to design. Papanek’s books include:

- Design for the Real World
- Design for Human Scale

We should also consider the contribution of Albertson and Faulkner.

Albertson and Faulkner: Appropriate Hard and Soft Technologies:

According to Dr. Maurice Albertson and Faulkner, appropriate hard technology is “engineering techniques, physical structures, and machinery that meet a need defined by a community, and utilize the material at hand or readily available. It can be built, operated and maintained by the local people with very limited outside assistance e.g., technical, material, or financial. It is usually related to an economic goal”. Some have explored the use of classroom projects for university-level physics students to research, develop and test appropriate hard technology (Buitenhuis

A. J., Zelenika I. and Pearce J. M.: 2010 pp.11-12).

Albertson and Faulkner consider “appropriate soft technology” as technology that deals with “the social structures, human interactive processes, and motivation techniques. It is the structure and process for social participation and action by individuals and groups in analyzing situations, making choices and engaging in choice-implementing behaviours that bring about change” (<http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/s10668-012-9337-9>).

The Water Decade: Village-Level Operation and Maintenance:

Water is the burning issue in our country even today after 60 years of independence. As India is a country of villages, we should think the problem of water in this case. Water pump is the offshoot of appropriate technology but in water decade, the condition was worst in India. There, we should see the key problem during water decade in India. Water pumps came to demonstrate the importance of appropriateness and context in the application of technology. During the International Drinking Water Decade (1981-1990), water wells with pumps were provided to villages in developing countries around the world, paid for primarily with foreign aid. This tended to be done in a top-down manner, with little attention to the local context. While claims are made for great strides in access to water, counter-claims are made that many of the water pump projects failed (Wikipedia: international Drinking Water).

A key problem was that the pumps were difficult to maintain at the village level - parts were not easily accessible or repairable, and or specialized skills were required that did not exist in the typical village. After the water decade, “village-level operation and maintenance” pumps, or VLOM pumps, were introduced. Such an

approach reduces the dependency of villages on governments and donors.

This lesson - the ability to maintain equipment locally - continues to be re-learned in many aid and development projects, decades on.

Paul Polak: The Death of Appropriate Technology Organisations:

More recently, Paul Polak stated that the flowering of the appropriate technology movement in decades past had no major impact on the poor, and many organizations devoted to appropriate technology have closed or scaled down.

He provocatively argues that the production of “appropriate technology” has died as the organisations producing appropriate technology did not emphasize on financial viability nor did they use using business models. In two blog posts on “The Death of Appropriate Technology” he states: The appropriate technology movement died because it was led by well-intentioned tinkerers instead of hard-nosed entrepreneurs designing for the market (http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Appropriate_technology).

He talks about technology for the poor, as distinct from the earlier appropriate technology movement which he argues did not take cost-effectiveness seriously, and therefore failed. However, initiatives such as Gunter Pauli’s Blue Economy project and products made by commercial companies (i.e. Tata Motors’ Tata Nano,) seem to show that there are still companies that do successfully marry low-cost design with keen business insight.

Appropedia: Appropriate Technology Goes Online:

Main article, Principles of appropriate technology. A new stage in appropriate technology has come with the introduction of the internet. The internet has facilitated the sharing of designs by AT

organizations. These designs were already open design, yet the sharing of the designs happened at too small a scale in the past. Designs of several devices or objects are now being shared across the internet using sites as appropedia, instructorless ... and reach people even outside the AT sector. In addition, kits and manuals sold by various organizations are now also being shared and help the poor in constructing complex, low-cost objects (<http://scholar.lib.vt.edu>).

China also implemented policies similar to appropriate technology during the reign of Mao Testing and the following cultural revolution. During the Cultural Revolution, development policies based on the idea of “walking on two legs” advocated the development of both large-scale factories and small-scale village industries (<http://scholar.lib.vt.edu>).

Conclusion:

In 21st century energy is one of the main inputs essential to the development of India. Energy technology is an important factor to prevent the degradation of the environment. So there is need to find alternatives to present path of the world's energy and environment.

Generally appropriate technology is proving sustainable development. It is small scale, labour intensive, energy efficient and most important thing is environmentally sound. In our country Mahatma Gandhi is the pioneer of this movement. His concept of ‘Self-Reliance’ or ‘Swadeshi’ is the heart of appropriate technology. He accepted the all rural development of man including spiritual which is very close to appropriate technology as a term appropriate technology was invented by E. F. Schumacher in his book, ‘Small is Beautiful’.

References:

1. Albertson, M. L. (1991): “Appropriate Technology,”

- Hydraulics Division ASCE, Nashville, Tenn.
2. Dhal and Pattnak, Binya (2012): “Appropriate Technology movement in india: An Emphatic Drift’, Sociology of Science and Technology, pp-85.
 3. Dalzell, H. W. (1981): “An Appropriate Technology for Indian Agriculture,” In Stonehouse (ed.) Biological Husbandry. Butterworth's: London.
 4. Kumar, H. D. (2002): “Environmental Technology and Biosphere Management,” Oxford and IBH publishing Co. Pvt., New Delhi.
 5. Willoughby, K.W. (1990): “Technology Choice: A Critique of the Appropriate Technology Movement”, London, Intermediate Technology Publications, ISBN 0-8133-7806-0, p. 72.
 6. Sianipar, C.P.M.; Yudoko, G.; Dowaki, K.; Adhiutama, A. (2013) : “Design methodology for Appropriate Technology: Engineering as if people mattered”, Sustainability 5 (8), 3382–3425.
 7. Evans, D. D. Gosh, P. K., ed. (1984): “Appropriate Technology in Third World Development”, London Greenwood Press, ISBN 0-313-24150-3, p. 40.
 8. Joshua M. Pearce, (2007) “Teaching Physics Using Appropriate Technology Projects”, the Physics Teacher, 45, pp. 164–167.
 9. Jackson, S. (1984 “Appropriate Technology in Third World Development”, Ghosh, P. K., Ed. London, Greenwood Press. p. 76. ISBN 0-313-24150-3.

Internet Website:

1. www.daervis.or.htm Retrieved 11/6/2024
2. <http://www.amazon.com> Retrieved 11/6/2024

3. [http://
www.daervis.org/introessat.htm](http://www.daervis.org/introessat.htm)
Retrieved 12/6/2024
4. <http://other90.cooperhewitt.org>
Retrieved 28/7/2024
5. <http://www.Tinytechindia.com>
Retrieved 28/7/2024
6. www.tve.org. Retrieved 28/7/ 2024
7. [http://lsa.colorado.edu/essence/texts/
appropriate.htm](http://lsa.colorado.edu/essence/texts/appropriate.htm) Retrieved 29/7/
2024
8. <http://www.fmreview.org/FMRpdfs>
Retrieved 14/9/2024
9. [http: // www.daervis.org](http://www.daervis.org)
Retrieved 21/6/2024
10. [http://www.ustechnologysolutions.c
om/](http://www.ustechnologysolutions.com/) Retrieved 28/7/2024
11. [http: //www.kiva.org](http://www.kiva.org). Retrieved
27/7/ 2024
12. [http://www appropedia.org](http://www.appropedia.org).
Retrieved 6/2/ 2024